

Association of two types of viruses with stunted, yellow rice plants in southern Sri Lanka

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Stunted rice plants with yellow discoloration were observed in maha season (Sep-Feb) 1986-87 in Monaragala and Hambantota districts. Insect transmission tests with brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* and green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens* showed that the disease can be transmitted to TNI plants by *N. virescens*.

The second youngest leaf of plants collected from affected fields were

Incidence of RTBV and RTSV in rice plants collected from fields in Angunukolapelessa Sri Lanka, 1986-87.

Location	Variety	Plants tested (no.)	Plants (%) infected with		
			RTBV+RTSV	RTBV	RTSV
Muthukandiya, Monaragala	BG94-1	20	75	20	5
	BG400-1	20	90	10	—
Medamulana, Hambantota	BG94-1	40	50	12.5	12.5
Angunulrolapelessa, Hambantota	BG94-1	10	10	60	30
	TNI (check)	10	0	0	0

homogenized individually. The sap was mixed with an equal amount of latex (Difco-Bacto Latex 0.81) suspension sensitized with antisera to rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) or rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) and shaken for 45 min. The presence of latex particle

clumps in the sap indicated virus antigens.

Most of the samples tested contain RTBV or RTSV alone or both (see table), indicating tungro disease and the association of RTBV and RTSV with tungro in Sri Lanka. □

Pest Control and Management

INSECTS

Biotype populations of *Nilaparvata lugens* in Hunan, China

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We collected brown planthopper (BPH) populations from 12 districts across Hunan Province during 1980-84 and 1986 to detect biotypes of *N. lugens*. Mudgo, ASD7, Ptb 33, Babawee, and Rathu Heenati were used as standard differential varieties. TNI was the susceptible check.

Germinated seeds were sown in a 60 × 30 × 10 cm seedbox with 5 cm row spacing, 3 replications per variety. A week after sowing, seedlings were thinned to 20/ row. Plants were infested with 5 second- or third-instar nymphs per seedling at the 2- to 3-leaf stage. Grading for plant damage began when 80% of the susceptible check plants were dead and was repeated twice, at 2-d intervals. The final rating was an average of the three gradings.

Damage in all but two differential varieties was below 3; ASD7 scored

Varietal reaction to populations of *N. lugens* collected in Hunan, China, 1980-86.

Collection site	Score ^a					
	TNI	Mudgo	ASD7	Ptb 33	Babawee	Rathu Heenati
			1980			
Changsha	9	1.3	1.6	1.5		
			1981			
Changsha	9	1.0	1.6	1.0		
Yueyang	9	1.0	1.0	1.0		
			1982			
Ningxiang	9	1.1	3.9	1.4		
Yiyang	9	1.7	3.0	1.0	1.0	
Changde	9	1.0	1.0	3.0		
Hengyang	9	1.2	1.1	2.2		
Xiangtan	9	1.3	3.9	2.0	2.2	
			1983			
Guiyang	9	1.0	1.0	3.0		
Lingling	9	2.3	2.3	2.3	1.0	
Shaoyang	9	1.0	1.6	1.6	1.6	
Huaihua	9	1.6	2.0	3.0	3.0	
Yongshun	9	2.3	1.3	3.0	3.6	
Changsha	9	0.3	1.3	0.6	0.6	
			1984			
Changsha	9	1.0	2.3	1.6	1.0	
			1986			
Yiyang	9	1.6	3.6	1.0	1.0	1.0
Changsha	9	1.0	1.6	1.6	1.0	1.0

^a 1-3 = resistant. 5-9 = susceptible.

below 3 with populations from 3 sites and Babawee with the population from Yongshun in 1983 (see table). All

populations of *N. lugens* in Hunan can be considered to belong to biotype 1.

In 1976, hybrid rice was first released